

Surface study of a shallow geothermal site for Abhé Geothermal Village Project (Djibouti)

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Abstract :

The site selected for the GV project in Djibouti Republic is isolated, 50 km from the National Grid and Electrical High Voltage line linking Ethiopia and Djibouti. The local population is pastoralist and semi-nomadic as the shore of the lake allow for permanent pastureland. Previously dispersed on the hills surrounding the lacustrine plain, the families tend to group around a school which opened a first class in October 2020.

The area - characterized by spectacular carbonaceous travertine chimneys built from hot-springs and fumarole hydrothermal deposits – was studied in the previous years for its geothermal potential in the perspective of electricity production for the national grid.

The target of the present geoscientific investigation was triple: (i) Medium-High temperature resource for electricity production with an ORC; (ii) Hot water production for direct uses applications including SPA and (iii) drinking water production for the village, the school and touristic installations. All resources targeted at shallow depths (a few ten to hundred metres). Field works included structural geology, volcanic petrology, hydrothermal mineralogy, and petrophysics, followed by laboratory studies.

One of the specificities of the project is the engagement – in parallel with the work on land - of a detailed drone survey for both the topography and structural geology (visible wavelength) carried on day-time and an Infra-Red survey producing a detailed mapping of the thermal vents carried in the night and early morning before sun-rise. This allowed to discover and measure the temperature of several geothermal vents unmapped and unsampled until now, then further measured and sampled for physical and chemical analysis. The Geochemical gas isotopic composition helps precise the magmatic origin of the heat source, whereas the water chemistry allows to map the hydrothermal plumbing including water mixing at shallow depth.

From the joint analysis of a large set of data: gravity, geological survey, satellite images interpretation and electric resistivity profiles, and the detailed magnetotellurics the 3D pictures of the geothermal fluid plumbing will be drawn. As a result, a geothermal conceptual model allows to propose shallow depth drilling sites and characteristics at for both electricity production from an ORC plant.

1. Introduction

The main objective of the Geothermal Village (GV) project, implemented within the EU-funded (H2020) LEAP-RE research & innovation program, is to introduce geothermal-based stand-alone electric and thermal energy systems to off-grid African communities. The GV concept proposes a geothermal exploitation in cascade mode, from electricity production from hot geothermal fluids to thermal energy direct use from lower temperature fluids for a large variety of applications, based on the local needs and income sources. 4 sites located in Eastern Africa were selected to engage interdisciplinary research that will lead to the feasibility demonstration of autonomous small-scale geothermal systems developed for and managed by African communities. The interdisciplinary research carried out in this project consists in geological, socio-economic and technical analyses of each site, in order to provide template case-studies on developing a suitable GV energy plan adapted to each local community needs and challenges.

The present paper focuses on the geosciences results obtained after field investigations of the Lake Abhé site study, located on the southwestern edge of the Djibouti Republic, near the Ethiopian border. These geosciences investigations, consisting in the first phase of the GV interdisciplinary research approach, aim to characterize the hydrogeological features and the geothermal reservoir dynamics of the target area. Given the size of the facilities and the power considered in the GV conceptual model (from 100 to 5000 kWe (Varet et al., 2020), the GV project is aiming at small targets, requiring a high-resolution characterization of the subsurface of the order of 1 km³. Alongside this detailed characterization, based in particular on geophysical surveys (magnetotellurics (MT), electric resistivity tomography (ERT)), a broader geological and geochemical study was also undertaken to meet this objective. The field work was carried out jointly by researchers from UL, UBO, Géo2D and IMAGIR, with the technical and scientific support and contribution of the ODDEG (the Djiboutian Geothermal Institute) in November 2021, after preparation works involving ODDEG and Géo2D in June and October 2021.

The Lake Abhé site population reaches 2,400 inhabitants on site and in the surrounding plain. Pastoralism (goats, sheep, camels) represents the area main activity, although a small tourism camp run by a local family is also present. These 2 local economic activities could benefit from the development of a GV, with a small ORC plant for electricity production (about 100 kWe), a local energy grid and shallow wells. This energy production would supply in particular the newly school built in 2020, the existing dispensary that is not operational yet and the tourism activity of this remarkable area. A balneotherapy station using the most suitable local geothermal water and mud is currently under study by the ODDEG and a specialized consultant. In addition, the short grass vegetation, developed on the sedimentary plain nearby the lake shore thanks to numerous hot-springs could be extended with an improved water management, including spring channeling and shallow well drilling.

2. Geological context

Lake Abhe is located near the center of the triple rift junction of the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden oceanic rifts with the continental East African Rift System (EARS), also marked by the nearby Dama Ale volcano, on the western shore of the lake in Ethiopia. It sits on the southern extremity of the NNW-SSE trending Tendaho graben, which itself extends southward from the Manda Harraro basaltic axial range, one of the most active spreading axes in Afar (Varet, 2018), and on the western extremity of the a-magmatic Gobaad graben trending WNW-ESE in the Djibouti Republic. The NNE-SSW Main Ethiopian Rift (MER), which is the northern segment of the EARS, abruptly stops when joining the Red Sea-Aden Rift system. It is characterized by an axial graben with recent fissure basaltic flows alternating with central silicic volcanoes.

The area selected for the project is floored by the basaltic stratoïd series (Figure 1a), which covers the whole floor in central Afar and was emitted 4 to 1 My ago, when the Gulf of Aden oceanic spreading segment penetrated the African continent through the Gulf of Tadjourah and ensured the junction with the Red Sea through Afar (Barberi et al., 1975). In the last period (circa 1My) a few rhyolitic centers were emitted topping the stratoïd series. The whole unit is affected by normal faults of WNW-ESE direction, with lacustrine sediments covering the lower parts of the outcrops, marking the successive periods of climate changes during the last 100 ky studied in detail by Gasse (1977).

Figure 1 : a) Lake Abhé site area selected for the GV project pictured in a red square on this section of the geological map of Afar (1/100.000; Varet, 1975). The stratoid series is figured in green, with associated rhyolite centers in orange. On the Ethiopian side (west of the lake), the Dama Ale volcano displays a succession of recent quaternary basalts (blue), intermediate lava flow (violet) and rhyolite domes (yellow) and pumice (orange). The orange line pictures the contour of the highest level of the lake (from Gasse, 1977) whereas the recent lacustrine and detrital sediments covering the Gobaad floor and the lake rims are in yellow ; b) Map of the studied area with location of the geophysical surveys and hot springs sampled for geochemical analyses.

Numerous thermal manifestations (steam vents, hot-springs, with temperature ranging from 70 to 100°C) are observed over the sedimentary basin in the continuation of faults NW-SE to WNW-ESE. This long-lasting active hydro-thermal system allowed the development of spectacular travertine chimneys which deposited in the last few tens of thousands years when the lake was at higher altitudes (DeMott et al., 2021). These chimneys are located in 2 main areas called Small Hydrothermal Chimneys area (SHCa) and Great Hydrothermal Chimneys area (GHGa), based on their morphology (Figure 1b).

3. A new data set

Structural, petrophysical, geochemical and geophysical data were acquired during and after the field work. Preliminary results are presented here after, they are used to propose a model.

3.1. *Structural data set*

As part of the structural survey of the studied area, structural lineaments were mapped using high-resolution remote sensing data and interpreted with knowledge from field geological observations. This work helps to decipher structural patterns of brittle structures (e.g. faults, fractures) developed within the volcanic series and the relationships with the hydrothermal chimneys distribution over the basin. Detailed lineament mapping was carried out on 2 digital elevation model (DEM) displayed on QGIS Version 3.22.6, using 2 different fixed viewing scale depending on the DEM resolution. Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Global DEM (30 m resolution) was used to map, over a large area, lineaments at the displaying scale of 1/60000. Focused on the main hydrothermal active area, a higher resolution DEM (0.5m resolution) was generated from Pléiades tri-stereo multispectral (MS) satellite imagery. This DEM was used to map structural lineaments of the volcanic series and hydrothermal chimneys alignments separately at the displaying scale of 1/10000. The overall result of the lineament mapping is represented on Figure 2, with the corresponding rose diagrams for the 3 lineament sets. These rose diagrams, generated with the *Line Direction Histogram* QGIS plugin represent lineaments orientation distribution in intervals of 10°. The length of the single bins of these diagrams corresponds

to the number of lineaments occurring in each of these intervals, weighted by the lineament length. In summary, 599 lineaments were mapped showing a ESE-WNW (090-120°) dominant lineament direction. Mapping carried out at the 1/10000 scale allows to identify other minor sets, with NNW-SSE and NE-SW orientations in the volcanic series and with N-S and ENE-SWS orientations for the chimneys alignment. These datasets suggest that fluid circulation that built the hydrothermal chimneys up are highly controlled by the brittle structures developed in the area.

Figure 2: Lineament map with the different scale of analysis

3.2. *Petrophysical data set*

Different rock facies were sampled in the basalt stratoid series outcropping east to the SHCa, depending on the vesicle content and the alteration level. The 7 analyzed samples are representative of the 3 main basalt facies recognized from petrological observation: fresh basalt, fresh vesicular basalt and altered basalt (Figure 3). Skeletal density, thermal conductivity (TC), permeability, P- and S-wave propagation velocity (V_P , V_S) were measured in this preliminary dataset. Later on, porosity and electricity in addition to these properties will be measured on larger set of samples to extend this petrophysical dataset.

The altered basalt facies show the lowest density and V_P , V_S values, and the highest permeability values. The vesicular basalt facies samples present intermediate values for V_P , V_S , permeability, density, and TC, with a rather high variability for these 3 latter properties. The fresh basalt facies samples show the highest values for V_P , V_S , TC and skeletal density. Permeability values are strongly variable. Overall, several fresh vesicular basalt layers seem to present good transfer properties and must be considered in the reservoir model.

Figure 3: Petrophysical data of 7 samples representative of three basalt facies. The section on the left represents an eruptive sequence of the basalt stratoid series.

3.3. Geochemical data set

Samples for gas chromatography and isotopes analyses ($^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$, $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$) of free gas, cold and hot springs were collected. We used copper tubes for $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ and $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ analyses while separate glass bottles were used to sample for chromatography and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$, respectively. Gas chromatography analysis was performed at INGV Palermo (Italy) and remaining analyses at CRPG (France). The gas composition shows that the main phase is N_2 (77.65 to 96.27%), followed by O_2 (0.24 to 20.7%), CO_2 (0.10 to 10.4%), and CH_4 (0.01 to 1.6%). Helium varies from 27 to 260 ppmV, CO from 1.30 to 69 ppmV, and H_2 from below detection limit to 61 ppmV, while C_2H_6 is only detected in two samples with 19 and 152 ppmV, respectively. Regarding isotopes, for the gas samples, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$ ranges from -8.18 to -4.82‰ which is within typical values for volcanic gases (Favara et al. 2002). Measured $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios range from 1.04 (± 0.02) to 8.58 (± 0.31) Ra (where Ra is the atmospheric $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratio of 1.39×10^{-6}) while $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ ranges from 0.30 to 14.7. The samples display a mixing between air that could be due to air contamination during sampling and the upper mantle typical ratio of ~ 8 Ra (Fig. 4).

In the Afar volcanic province, $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios can reach up to 20 Ra, indicating the presence of a deep ^3He rich mantle plume (Marty et al., 1996; Pik et al. 2006). However, the results we obtained appear in the range of upper mantle composition (8 ± 2 Ra) and above the range of the continental lithospheric mantle (5 ± 2 Ra). Such results are below those expected for the Afar region, considering that in the Tendaho Graben (~ 110 km NW) and in the shore of Lake Asal (~ 80 km NE) higher ratios have been described (11 to 13 Ra; Marty et al., 1996; Scarsi & Craig 1996). However, considering the low $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ values close to air, it is possible that the local mantle endmember is even higher than the typical MORB value in the Abhé region.

Figure 4 : On the left, location of samples and on the right, R/Ra versus $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ plot. All samples plot along a mixing line between air and upper mantle components. Blue represents water samples and red the free gas ones; circles are samples from the SHCa and triangles from the GHCa domain.

Although the gas shows a volcanic signature both for noble gases and for CO_2 , the low concentration of the later can indicate secondary processes that concentrate N_2 in the gas phase. This process could result from preferential dissolution of CO_2 in water compared to N_2 and/or via carbonate precipitation during transportation of the gas phase.

Degassing occurs in two domains named SHCa and GHCa (Figure 1b); however, both display similar gas compositions and isotopic signatures that indicate a common hydrothermal system at depth, dominated by a magmatic source. This result agrees with the model previously proposed by Awaleh et al. (2015), based on water chemistry and stable isotope analyses, in which the authors propose a common reservoir for both areas based on the transport of heat from depth with the hydrothermal system being fed by meteoric water from the regional aquifer. These authors found very low tritium contents and low deuterium values compatible with an older and deeper water source than that of surface waters. Considering that the Abhé geothermal system is fed by a regional-scale aquifer system rather than a local and superficial one, its most likely source of heat is the Dama Ali volcanic system, ~ 30 km W of our study area.

3.4. Geophysical data set

3.4.1. Electrical investigations

18 electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) profiles, each 610m long, have been implemented with the aim of looking for resistivity and chargeability data from ground level to a 100m depth over the hydrothermal interest area. The structural network guiding fluid flow has been described in terms of alteration, as well as the lithological interface, being a potential geotechnical issue for the stability of future drilling operations.

From those 18 profiles, the following profile G42 is considered as the most representative of the different signatures found on site (Figure 5). This section was deployed in the SHCa (Figure 1b), and highlight fluid circulation in the subsurface of this active area.

Figure 5: Tomography sections of resistivity, chargeability and normalized chargeability, profile G42.

Figure 6: Distribution of inverted conductivity and analysis in conjunction with normalized chargeability

The use of normalized chargeability as demonstrated by Revil and Gresse (2021), allows to distinguish chargeability signatures due to clays from chargeability due to metallic particles (Figure 6). Then it is possible to identify high cationic exchange capacity formation (when surface conductivity predominates), corresponding to the rise of alteration clay volume fraction.

Knowing the fracture control on the fluid flow path from field observation, thanks to the detection of alteration clays and the detection of the sediment/basalt interface, it is possible to recognize fault structures and hydrothermal fluid paths. A 3D model including fluid distribution along this interface and the shallow faults identified in the SHCa in under development, in order to manage geotechnical exploration and drilling stability problematics.

3.4.2. The magneto-telluric (MT) data set

A high density array of 21 MT sites was deployed, with spacing ranging from 250-500m completed by 11 existing MT soundings provided by ODDEG, in order to characterize the subsurface electric structure at a fine scale. We performed the 3D modeling of the MT array with *minim3D* 3D inversion software (Hautot et al., 2007).

The inversion scheme is based on a steepest descent technique to minimize a misfit function plus regularization terms. The technique does not involve any Jacobian or Hessian estimates. Hence, the inversion grid and the forward computation grid are disjoint which provides a strong degree of flexibility to adjust the inversion grid and the regularization with respect to the data number and distribution. The 3-D inversion uses the full impedance tensor at all frequencies and sites. The minimum horizontal dimensions of the meshes are 110x110 m with the GV project area of study, 220 x 220m outside. The surface of the 3D model is 2.9 (NS) x 3.3 (EW) km and a maximum depth of 4 km to account for the longest period data (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Left: MT array, yellow pins the MT sites from November 2021 survey; blue pins: existing MT data provided by ODDEG. Right: The 3-D block for inversion: in black the grid for the forward calculation and in red the inversion grid

As an example of the resulting model, we present 2 vertical sections in Figure 8 down to 1 km depicting a surface low resistive layer, extension of the shallow conductor observed in the DC models. A deep conductive structure which may be assimilated to a fracture zone connected to this shallow conductor is observed in the NS section, East of the model. This conductor suggested the presence of ascendant hot fluids feeding the shallow layer. We are currently in the process to interpret these structures in terms of geothermal conceptual modelling.

Figure 8: EW (A) and NS (B) vertical cross sections from the 3-D resistivity model. The green square indicated the Lake Abhe village for reference.

3.5. The UAV Thermal-infrared imaging

In order to find and estimate the position of hydrothermal sources, we drew a thermal map of different spots from UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) Thermal-infrared (TIR) imaging survey; we used a small UAV (DJI MAVIC 2 Entreprise Advanced) (location on figure 1). It has 2 cameras, one with an uncooled TIR Sensor (resolution 640 x 512, temperature accuracy $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the other with optical sensor (resolution 8 000 x 6 000, equivalent focal: 24mm). We deployed UAV around chimneys in one site of the SHCa and 2 sites of the GHCa (Figures 9 to 11). We have measured temperatures from 84 events of hydrothermal sources. After post-processing that consists to correct radiometry and emissivity from raw UAV TIR and ground data, temperatures range between 43°C and 100°C.

Figure 9: The “Great Axe” located in the SHCa (see location on Figure 1)

Figure 10: The “Château-fort” located in the GHCa (see location on Figure 1)

Figure 11: The “Great western chimney” located in the GHCa (see location on Figure 1)

Thermal Map of the Great western chimney

4. Geological model and future development

From the geosciences investigations presented above, the more relevant results are:

- the fault and fracture network is predominantly composed ESE-striking structures, connected by minor oblique structures.
- Several layers in the volcanic sequences with vesicular structures and/or altered facies have high porosity and permeability.
- The geochemical composition of gazes and fluids of hydrothermal sources highlights a deeper origin of the fluids with a mantle contribution.
- The deep and shallow plumbing systems are recognized by low resistivity signature on MT and on ERT data respectively.
- The surface manifestations of these conduits are confirmed by thermal mapping by drone.

A preliminary schema is built. The hydrothermal surface manifestation are directly linked to the sub-surface fluid circulation features observed through geophysics surveys, composed of horizontal and vertical conduits. MT data highlight a deep zone of ascending fluids that reaches surface thanks to vertical conduits that could be formed by the fault and fractures and more specifically by their intersection (cf. high IP anomalies, Figure 12). Fluid transfer may also be enhanced by horizontal conduits consisting in vesicular lava flows and/or altered levels.

Figure 12: Interpreted structural control thanks to geophysical and geological data

The 3D geothermal model is currently under development, in view of determining the 3 drilling targets of this GV project: (a) a medium enthalpy reservoir for electricity production; (b) low enthalpy resources for thermal energy direct use including thermal baths and spa, and (c) drinkable water production. In parallel, the socio-economic studies are engaged to precise the needs of the local communities and future developments on site, and the way the project will be implemented by ODDEG in partnership with local authorities. In the following months, a feasibility study will be conducted including the engineering schemes.

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